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Performance level of caregivers and its relationship with some variables

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Abstract

There is an urgent for an immediate action if the goals of the Safe Motherhood Initiative are to be achieved .As one of four pillars of Safe Motherhood includes Antenatal Care(ANC), therefore this study is mainly concerned with (ANC)performance that is provided through caregivers at primary health care centers (PHCCs) .In order to describe Antenatal care (ANC) performance of the caregivers in Baghdad PHCCs sectors and to determine the relationship between the performance level of caregivers with some variables such as, age, level of education, years of experience and training sessions of caregivers.

Material and Methods : Descriptive cross sectional fields study to describe Antenatal care (ANC) performance of the caregivers in Baghdad PHCCs sectors .

It started on the 4th of April 1997 and continued up to the 23rd of June 1997. The study includes two part instruments conducted; demographical datasheet and observational checklist.

Results: The sample consisted of 132 caregivers at 20 Primary Health Care Centers (PHCCs) in (5) Baghdad PHC sectors chosen randomly.

The data analysis revealed that there were big differences between the actual working observed and standardized

numbers among nurses, health auxiliaries and clerks.

The coverage rate for the 4th visit and above it of the pregnant woman to PHCC was 31.4%. The study showed that the nurses had a good performance, the health auxiliaries and clerk as well in one of PHC sectors only. While in terms of physical examination activity by physicians ; the B.P showed 86.2% and 93.5% was of the fund height level in abdominal examination activity, but fetal heart sound was 9.8% at this examination.

Discussion and Recommendations:

The study recommended to emphasis on the number and quality of the training courses together with feedback information and to provide PHC sectors with the required man power.

Introduction

There is an urgent for an immediate action if the goals of the Safe Motherhood Initiative are to be achieved .As one of four pillars of Safe Motherhood includes Antenatal Care(ANC), therefore this study is mainly concerned with (ANC)performance that is provided through caregivers at primary health care centers (PHCCs) . Thus the need has emerged to assess the level of antenatal caregiver's performance. In addition it is the key stone of modern obstetrics that is

routinely provided for all pregnant women at primary care level from screening to intensive life support while pregnant and up to delivery (Rooney,1992). Moreover several health organizations and recent reviews of literature gave a high priority to improve mothers' health by early detection and treatment of abnormalities that affect their health or their babies to successful childbearing and adequate preparations for labour and lactation (WHO,1992). In order to describe Antenatal care (ANC) performance of the caregivers in Baghdad PHCCs sectors by providing health services to women during their pregnancy and to determine the relationship between the performance level of caregivers with some variables such as, age, level of education, years of experience and training sessions of caregivers.

Materials and Methods

A descriptive cross sectional field study using simple random sample was conducted on different professional categories who were dealing with pregnant woman, so as to assess and describe antenatal care (ANC) performance of the caregiver at primary health care centers (PHCCs). It adopts the following process:

Administrative arrangements , instrument construction, setting of the study, validity, pilot study, reliability of an instrument, data collection, implementation, data processing and statistical analysis.

Instrument construction:

A two-part instrument was constructed, it consisted of the following:

1- Participant information :

Developed to obtain general information of participants including

their age, level of education, years of experience and the number and the period of training courses in the field of practice.

2- Observation checklist:

Five observational checklists were designed for each activity of (ANC) clinic to assess caregivers' performance. Each item has yes and no options to be checked by the investigator. Every option rated on a 3-point type likert scale as (weak,moderate,good).(polite,1995) The three observations were divided into weak level of performance to be bellow 50 marks, (50-75) marks were for moderate performance level and (75-100) marks were for good performance.

Setting of the study:

20 PHC centers , were selected randomly from 101 PHC centers in five Baghdad Sectors such as Al-Adhamia , Al-Rusafa , Al-Karkh, Al-Kadhmia and Al Sader City Sectors ; these represent about 20% of the total number of (PHC) centers.

Selection of the sample:

The study sample consisted of 132 caregivers at the selected 20 (PHCCs) .

Validity of the instrument:

The content validity of an instrument is based on the principle of judgment. Experts in the content may be called on to analyze the items to see if they represented adequately. (Polit, 1995).

Some notes and opinions that were added by experts were coded and tabulated. The instrument was therefore valid since all the notes were introduced.

Reliability of an instrument :

Reliability refers to the stability, consistency, accuracy and dependability of the instrument (Tones & Tilford, 1994).

To check the interrator reliability of the observation checklist, the investigator and her colleague were

observing the caregivers of different categories at the same time by using the same sheet of checklist. These observations were implemented on 15 caregivers. They were distributed across three PHC centers. Each PHC center represented a PHC Sector in Baghdad City. Internal consistency reliability was established for the observation checklist, the results showed that reliability coefficient (R) was 0.86 which indicated that the checklist was adequately reliable for the study.

Data Collection :

Data were gathered by the use of structured interviews and a checklist which was specified for each category of caregivers . Data were collected between the 4th of April 1997 and the 23rd of June 1997.

Implementation:

At the beginning the investigator made herself as an active participant and trying to learn from them and observe them, and interacting as a student with them accordingly with out interfering with their activities. Sometimes caregivers asked the investigator to do things, and she did it. Thus three observations of performance was made for every skill performed by each caregiver according to the type of activity. This division was applied to all categories of caregivers in order to determine the line of achieving activities evidently.

Data processing and analysis :

Information from the instrument was recorded into a tally sheet from which it was analyzed.

Statistical analysis:

1. Descriptive statistics :-

A-tables

B-Rates

2. Inferential statistics :-

C-Regression analysis (simple linear model) Al-Jiboory, 1991.

D-Person product correlation coefficient to estimate the scale reliability (Hinke, 1982) .

There was a set of probability levels to determine the significance of the test a:

(1)Non significant (NS)($P \geq 0.05$).

(2) Significant (S)($P \leq 0.05$) .

(3) High significant (HS)($P \leq 0.01$).

(R) In Regression analysis test means coefficient determination which explain the degree of effectiveness of the independent variable (number of training courses) on the degree of changes occurring to dependent variable (performance) (Polit, 1995).

The results

Table No. (1): Distribution of the caregivers by age, level of education, years of experience and their training at PHCCs in Baghdad (n=132)

Caregivers Categories	Physicians	Nurses	Medical Assistants	Health Auxiliaries	Clerks	Total	Percent
Age							
20-30	0	1	15	5	5	26	19.7
31-40	25	3	12	14	9	63	47.7
41-50	16	5	4	13	2	40	30.3
>50	0	0	0	3	0	3	2.3
Total	41	9	31	35	16	132	100
Educational Status							
Primary School Graduates	0	0	0	9	4	13	9.9
Intermediate School Graduates	0	6	0	20	5	31	23.5
Secondary School Graduates	0	2	0	5	7	14	10.6
Institute Graduates	0	0	30	1	0	31	23.5
College Graduates	37	1	0	0	0	38	28.8
Post Based Graduates	4	0	1	0	0	5	3.8
Total	41	9	31	35	16	132	100
Years of Experience							
<1	0	2	2	0	2	6	4.6
1-10	27	4	27	19	9	86	65.2
11-20	13	3	1	12	5	34	25.8
21-30	1	0	1	3	0	5	3.8
>31	0	0	0	1	0	1	1.5
Total	41	9	31	35	16	132	100
No of MCH Training Courses Participations							
One course	7	0	2	3	1	13	9.9
Two courses	2	3	2	3	1	11	8.3
Three courses	3	1	0	4	3	11	8.3
More than three courses	28	2	21	24	6	81	61.4
Total	40	6	25	34	11	116	87.9

Note: Total Number (116) of participants doesn't mean the total number of caregivers in the sample.

Table No.(2):The relationship between the ages of caregivers and their performance level .

caregivers	performance level Age categories	Weak F.	Moderate F.	Good F.	Comparative significance
Physicians	30-34	2	2	-	(0.33)
	35-39	14	5	-	(0.40**)
	40-44	4	2	-	(0.33)
	45-49	6	2	-	(0.42)
	50	2	2	-	(0.33)
Nurses	28-34	-	1	1	(0.33)
	35-41	-	1	1	(0.33)
	42-48	-	3	2	(0.33)
Medical Assistants	21-26	3	1	3	(0.10)
	27-32	3	2	7	(0.25)
	33-38	2	-	2	(0.16)
	39-44	1	1	4	(0.33)
	45-50	2	-	-	(0.67*)
Health Auxiliaries	27-32	1	3	2	(0.17)
	33-38	-	2	2	(0.33)
	39-44	1	3	2	(0.17)
	45-50	1	3	4	(0.21)
	50<	-	-	2	(0.67*)
Clerks	25-30	1	3	1	(0.13)
	31-36	1	2	4	(0.24)
	37-42	-	2	-	(0.33)
	43<	-	1	1	(0.33)

Table No.2 demonstrates the relationship between the categories mentioned above and their ages, in which there was a high significant association (0.40) between the physicians' performance level and their ages ranging (35-39)years old at level $P \leq 0.01$ concerning medical assistants a significant relationship

(0.67*)at level $P \leq 0.05$ on weak level of performance of ages ranged between (45-50) years old . a significant differences(0.67*) at level $P \leq 0.05$ for Health Auxiliaries of more than 50 years old

Table No. (3): The relationship between the educational status of caregivers and their performance level.

caregivers	performance level	Weak F.	Moderate F.	Good F.	C.S
	education status				
Physicians	College Graduates	24	13	0	(0.33**)
	Post Based Graduates	4	0	0	(0.67*)
Nurses	Intermediate School Graduates	0	3	3	(0.33)
	Secondary School Graduates	0	1	1	(0.33)
	College Graduates	0	0	1	(0.67)
Medical Assistants	Institute Graduates	10	5	15	(0.17)
	Post Based Graduates	1	0	0	(0.67)
Health Auxiliaries	Primary School Graduates	1	3	5	(0.22)
	Intermediate School Graduates	4	8	8	(0.13)
	Secondary School Graduates	0	2	3	(0.33)
	Institute Graduates	1	0	0	(0.67)
Clerks	Primary School Graduates	0	1	3	(0.13)
	Intermediate School Graduates	1	3	1	(0.13)
	Secondary School Graduates	1	4	2	(0.19)

This table shows a highly significant association (0.33) at level $P \leq 0.01$ concerning medical college graduates and their performance. The same table

also demonstrates a significant differences (0.67) at level $P \leq 0.05$ regarding postgraduates .C.S means Comparative significance.

Table No.(4) : Relationship between years of experience of caregivers and their level of performance.

caregivers	performance level	Weak F.	Moderate F.	Good F.	Comparative significance
	years of experience				
Physicians	1-10	19	8	-	(0.37**)
	11-20	9	4	-	(0.36)
	21-30	-	1	-	(0.33)
Nurses	1>	-	1	-	(0.33)
	1-10	-	1	4	(0.42)
	11-20	-	1	2	(0.33)
Medical Assistants	1>	1	-	1	(0.17)
	1-10	8	4	15	(0.22)
	11-20	1	-	-	(0.67)
	21-30	1	-	-	(0.67)

Health Auxiliaries	1-10	4	6	9	(0.14)
	11-20	1	7	4	(0.25)
	21-30	-	1	2	(0.33)
	31>	-	-	1	(0.67)
Clerks	1>	-	1	1	(0.33)
	1-10	2	5	2	(0.11)
	11-20	-	2	3	(0.33)

this table revealed that a highly significant relationship between years of experience and performance for

physicians only (0.37) at level $P \leq 0.01$ of (1-10) years .

Table No.(5):The effect of the training courses length on the performance for all categories of caregivers .

Categories of caregivers	Training courses (≥ 3 & < 3)*	Beta (slope)	T value	Prob. Level	Correlation coefficient	R-squared	No. of training courses
Physicians	≥ 3	1.59	(0.53)	(0.60)	0.09	0.7%	25
	< 3	-2.92	(-0.68)	(0.50)	-0.11	1.2%	56
Nurses	≥ 3	-26.08	(4.93)	(1.6E-5**)	0.62	38.4%	10
	< 3	49.95	(10.94)	(1.8E-3**)	0.87	75.4%	10
Medical Assistants	≥ 3	1.11	(0.94)	(0.35)	0.15	2.2%	13
	< 3	22.37	(3.29)	(2.1E-3**)	0.47	21.8%	34
Health Auxiliaries	≥ 3	11.23	(2.56)	(0.01 **)	0.37	14.04%	39
	< 3	27.77	(5.16)	(7.2E-8**)	0.63	39.9%	44
Clerks	≥ 3	26.14	(3.94)	(3.3E-4 **)	0.53	28.5%	12
	< 3	42.59	(6.59)	(7.9E-8**)	0.73	52.7%	13

Note : * 3 days and above for courses with symbol ≥ 3 , and below of 3 days for courses with symbol < 3 . The highest significant relationship between the level of performance and the duration of training courses was for the nurses. It was (1.6E-5) at $P < 0.001$ for ≥ 3 days participation in these courses, while it was (1.8E-13)at $P < 0.001$ for < 3 days participation in these courses .

Discussion:

The findings of the study indicated that the majority 47.7% (63) of caregivers were aged 31-40 years old which may be a good age for productivity, while the age of more than 50 years old formed the minority 2.23% (3). In regard to educational status of the subjects they were different Table No. (1).

Among (41) physicians only (4) of them were of post based graduates, and

the remaining (37) were of college graduates. In contrary to the findings of our study, the results of Fadhil's study (1987), revealed a higher score (4) of post based graduate level compared with only (9) physicians who had basic medical college qualification. Among (9) nurses, the majority of them (8) were of secondary and intermediate school graduates, leaving only (1) with higher education level college graduate.

In contrast to this finding, Fadhil's (1987) found that (7) professional nurses were distributed among (6) centers, which were considered better coverage in those centers. While most of medical assistants (31) of them were institute graduates. Then the auxiliaries and clerks were distributed between secondary school graduates and below, where as Fadhil's (1987) showed that categories such as auxiliary nurses or vaccinators had primary education only. With respect to the years of experience it seemed that the majority 65.15 % (86) of all caregivers who had experience were between (1-10) years, which means that the sample may had taken moderate years of practice in their work. While the 3.8 (5) of physician, medical assistants, auxiliaries had (21-30) years of experience.

In support to this study, Fadhil's (1987) found that most of physicians working at PHCCs have had more than six years of experience since qualification. The longest qualified physician was 21 years of experience. The same study showed that the health visitors working at MCH centers had been qualified between (7) and (14) years of experience and the professional nurses were qualified between (9) to (12) years of experience.

Other categories of caregivers such as vaccinators or auxiliary nurses had six years of primary education and special training courses were ranging from (3) to (18) months.

As regards other categories of caregivers in the present study, the longest period of experience to the physicians and nurses was (18) years, to the medical assistants (23) years of experience, to health auxiliaries (33) years of experience, with respect to health visitors and to clerks (15) years of experience, while the most recent

qualified were for the physicians (1) year and the nurses (9) months of experience, medical assistants (3) months, health auxiliaries (1) years and clerks (2) months of experience during the present study. That indicated a big gap of the experience years among each category of personnel.

In terms of training courses, it appeared from this table that the highest percentage in participating of all caregivers (132) was 61.4% for those who attended courses for more than three courses, for caregivers who were working for the last three years.

It has been noticed that it can be considered as a good indication of training. Through these courses practical knowledge done by the trainees to change their trends and attitudes in these courses were added to that the evaluation at the end of the course except, courses that extended three days and less. In Abdul Jabar & Khawa's survey (1997) conducted on 574 caregivers to evaluate their work performance at PHC centers in six Iraqi Governorates. It was revealed that 63% of the staff were included in the survey participated in training courses. This finding was decreased to the results of this study which represented 87% of the total participation in training courses. Since, the present study found that the physicians number the highest percentage 31.1% (41), and the lowest percentage were reflected by the nurses 6.8%(9), it seems that the nurses were in desperate need for participating more in training courses.

In support of our study results, Abdul Jabar & Khawla,s survey (1997) which was carried out to evaluate MCH work performance, showed that the highest percent 34.2% (216) was of physicians which was less than the results of our study because of sample size. Regarding nursing category they accounted for 26.2% (147) which was close to the present study finding. We can notice that the results of both studies are approximately similar.

The relationship between the age of caregivers and their level of performance: When a relationship was established between the ages of caregivers and their performance level the investigator had realized that the relationship between the ages of physician and level of performance on its moderate or weak level, was highly significant at level $p < = 0.01$ for ages between (35-39) years old. That is probably due to lack of awareness and motivation both moral and financial. This can be achieved by fostering them into training courses, in which new policies of MOH will be explored to them which may help to ensure their engagement in work. There was also a significant relationship at level $p < = 0.05$ of health auxiliaries for age of more than 50 years old, which was on good level of performance. While medical assistants at ages between (45-50) showed significant differences at level $p < = 0.05$ but on the weak level of performance, it means that their output was affected by their ages Table No.(2) .

The relationship between the educational status of caregivers and their level of performance: Concerning the relationship between the educational status of caregivers and their performance level. Findings of the study indicated that there were high significant differences at level $p < = 0.01$ through testing the observed and expected frequencies concerning college graduate physicians on weak and moderate levels of work. That indicated negative attitude toward performance which was clear at weak level (table No.3).

In addition to that there was a statistical significant association at level $p < = 0.05$ found for post based graduates through testing the observed and expected frequencies on their weak level

of performance. This finding was unexpected since good performance should be achieved when there is scientific specialization, a case which is considered confusing because it is illogical event. The investigator believed that this situation came up in our country for the circumstances of sanction. That caused loose of motivation and default in some of their duties. Therefore other qualified categories like nurses, medical assistants should be allowed more to do normal activities, as it is wrong for higher trained staff to spend time doing things that others can do as stated by (wood, et al., 1981).

(Stanhope & Lancaster, 1996) mentioned also that studies have shown that 60% to 80% of primary care traditionally done by physicians, can be delivered by nurse practitioner for less money and with equal or better quality. The author's point of view supported these concepts to let physicians be more interested in managing serious cases of clients and decrease the work load they face.

Moreover, in a paper written by (Ryan et al., 1997) to assess benefits of two alternative forms of ANC G.P/midwife, the results suggest willingness to pay of pounds b2500 for ANC, with no significant differences between the types of care provided.

Relationship between years of experience of caregivers and their level of performance: As for the effect of the years of experience of caregivers on their performance level (table No.4) the results indicated highly significant differences at level $p < = 0.01$ of physician's performance to their years of experience (1-10).

The same table demonstrated non significance at level $p > = 0.05$ among nurses, medical assistants, auxiliaries and clerks on all levels of performance against all levels of their years of experience. These findings are practically unacceptable.

However from the author's point of view, caregivers are always in need of more motivation and encouragement in their field of practice in order to maintain good and satisfactory performance. And perhaps there is a need to make review of evaluating application through and after the training courses accomplishment in order to overcome the obstacles that may be developed. In service programs need to include evaluation of participant satisfaction, learning and application to clinical practice. (Alspach, 1995).

Since the performance level depends in most cases on the health personnel training in the courses, the length of these courses spent and the number of these courses in a year. Then not necessarily for performance depends on years of experience, although it is significant factor. Joan & Bentley stated that obstetrician should receive training in appropriate practice situations. The major deficiency is the lack of suitable training placement and support of midwives (WHO, 1991).

The effect of the training courses length on the performance for all categories of caregivers: Table No (5) demonstrated a simple linear model of a regression test for the performance of all caregivers categories. This test conducted a measure of the effect of different courses toward performance. There were two in dependable variables, they comprised courses which extended more than 3 days marked by >3 days, and courses which were less than 3 days pointed by a symbol of <3 days. This table showed that there was an effect of training courses (≥ 3 days) on nurse's performance (dependent variable) representing 38.4% which was regarded the highest percentage among other caregivers. These courses were

considered as dominant factors of the effectiveness on nurse's performance. There were many factors intervening and affecting their performance among which the carelessness to engage nurses into suitable courses through the responsible staff, or the load of work in the ANC clinic. In addition these courses (≥ 3 days) represented high significant association at level $p \leq 0.01$, T-value (4.93) and correlation coefficient (R) (0.62), that means that they need training courses of more than 3 days. A strong effect of < 3 days represented 75.4% on the nurse's performance, was considered the highest percentile among the other caregivers. Moreover a high significant relationship at level $p \leq 0.01$, T-value (10.9) and (R) (0.87).

In support of this finding (Tiendrebeogo, et al.1996), revealed that the rise in the number of health agents to be trained has led to the arrangements of short-term courses. So as MOH, (1992-1997) applied this policy. That means also these courses (< 3 days) had a good effects on nurse's performance. Although they had minimum requirements of giving educational information (MOH, 1997). Therefore it should emphasis more knowledge and practice during these courses. This can be achieved by implementation of > 3 days training courses. Relative to clerks, auxiliaries and medical assistants for courses of < 3 days representing 52.7% 39.9% and 21.8% respectively were accounted (6.59), (5.16) and (3.29) which were highly significant. That interpreting the lack in application work procedures and may be that need more follow up after have being back into work place. Concerning > 3 days training courses for clerks, and auxiliaries. They had high significant relationship at level $p \leq 0.01$ with T-value (3.24) for clerks, and T. value (2.56) for auxiliaries. While their performance were affected by these courses (≥ 3 days) in 28.5% and

14.04%. (Abdul Jabar& Khawla 1997) carried out a study on 574 caregivers in PHCCs in Iraq it revealed that 65% of most courses held for the staff, lasted for 3 days, that means more than two thirds of caregivers had participated for 3 days courses. Despite MOH (1985) recommended that caregivers should be involved into intensive training courses and maintaining continuous follow up to them especially those caregivers who have been in desperate need to these courses. Unfortunately the physicians demonstrated lowest percentage of effect on performance 0.72% although they were good participants in training courses that they achieved the highest percentile in the number of these courses as it showed in table no (4) among the other caregiver. That indication that some factors interfere in the situation of the effect on performance like incentives, materials, transportation or others..... Finally a confirmation upon teaching and training courses should take place to all caregivers in order to support their skills. Because these courses will give more knowledge and more practice (12 hours theory and 12 hours practice with an evaluation at the end of the course)as an example to small courses (MOH, 1997).

Conclusions:

According to the findings of this study and their interpretations, the investigator has come up with the following Conclusions:

1. There was shortage in the numbers of nurses, health auxiliaries and clerks in all PHC sectors in Baghdad according to standardized values, whereas there was some shortage in medical personnel numbers in Saddam PHC sector in Baghdad.

2. Most ANC personnel were of young age group (31-40) years old, and with experience of (1-10) years in the field of practice . And about 1/3rd of the sample were college graduates who were medical personnel. In addition to that, over 2/3rds of all the sample had participated in the training courses for more than (3) courses of participations.

3. There was weak to moderate performance level of medical personnel who were working in 2/5ths of PHC sectors, while it was not significant for the other personnel as regards educational status.

4. Duration of training courses moved toward those with less than 3 days which affected the quality of these courses and consequently the performance level of caregivers. It revealed that the nurses were the highest category who was affected by those courses.

Recommendation:

Based on the stated conclusions, the study recommended that:

- 1.PHC sectors should be provided with the required manpower and/or redistribution of the available personnel according to the catchment's area of each PHCC.

- 2.The number of training courses and arrangement of time table for participation for personnel involved in ANC to ensure equal opportunities for them should be concentrated on.

- 3.The training courses must concentrate in their syllabuses on the practical activities in order to enhance the performance level of the trainees.

- 4.The quality of the training courses should be emphasized by providing adequate time with the presence of time table for the relevant subjects and setting clear objectives for the training courses with serious evaluation.

- 5.Feedback information should be provided to explore benefits of the training courses

and regular supervision should be directed to PHCCs on ANC personnel.

6. Encourage studies and surveys to detect problems at the level of PHCCs with emphasis on ANC area.

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